

Preregistration: Directional Forecast Accuracy Study (Walmart M5)

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Date: [to be filled on upload]

1. Study Title

Directional Forecast Accuracy Across Hierarchical Aggregations Using Walmart M5 Data

2. Purpose and Context

This study investigates how forecast aggregation structure affects directional accuracy in hierarchical demand forecasting.

Using the publicly available **Walmart M5 forecasting dataset**, the analysis compares **Bottom-Up (BU)** forecasts and **Top-Down (TD)** forecasts across product and location hierarchies.

The goal is to quantify not just the difference in error magnitude, but the **directional reliability**—how often BU forecasts outperform TD forecasts in weekly accuracy comparisons—and the statistical significance of that advantage.

This preregistration defines the data scope, forecast generation process, evaluation metrics, and planned significance tests.

3. Dataset

Source:

Walmart M5 Forecasting — Accuracy Competition (Makridakis et al., Kaggle, 2020).

Files used:

- sales_train_validation.csv
- calendar.csv
- sell_prices.csv

Structure:

Merged into one long-format table where each row represents a single **store × item × date** record with:

- state_id, store_id, cat_id, dept_id, item_id, date, wm_yr_wk,
- units, sell_price_raw, and computed revenue.

Aggregation hierarchy:

- Product: `Food`, `Hobbies`, `Household` (each with 2–3 subcategories + totals).
 - Location: 10 stores (CA, TX, WI), 3 regional roll-ups, and total.
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4. Forecast Generation

Forecast horizon: Monthly.

Each monthly forecast uses only data strictly prior to that month's start date.

Evaluation frequency: Weekly.

Forecast accuracy is computed for each week within the forecast month.

Models:

1. **ARIMA** — primary model (main reported results).
2. **Simple Exponential Smoothing (SES)** — supporting.
3. **Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing (HWES)** — supporting.

Each model produces both BU and TD forecasts across all store × category combinations.

5. Evaluation Metrics

Primary metric: Mean Absolute Error (**MAE**) — used for all directional and magnitude comparisons reported in main tables.

Supporting metrics: Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (**sMAPE**) and Root Mean Square Error (**RMSE**) — reported in Appendix tables for robustness checks.

All analyses will be run separately for:

- **Units** (volume forecasts).
 - **Revenue** (value forecasts).
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6. Analysis Plan

Week–Month Boundary Handling. Evaluation is performed at the **day level** and restricted to **calendar-month days only**. Weekly metrics for each `wm_yr_wk` are then computed **using only the days of that week that fall within the forecast month**; weeks that cross month boundaries are **split** (partial weeks at the start/end of a month are permitted). Directional hits and weekly % differences are derived from these **within-month weekly aggregates**. Month-level significance tests use the **number of evaluation weeks** (including partials) in that month.

Step 1: Weekly Accuracy Aggregation

Compute weekly MAE, sMAPE, and RMSE for BU and TD forecasts for every store × category × model.

Step 2: Directional “Hit” Identification

For each week:

- Hit = 1 if BU < TD (for the given metric)
- Hit = 0 otherwise

Step 3: Statistical Tests

Objective	Test	Result Reported
Directional consistency	Binomial test ($H_0 = 0.5$)	<i>Binom p</i>
Magnitude of improvement	One-sample t-test ($H_0 = 0$) on weekly % differences	<i>t p</i>

Both tests run for Units and Revenue separately.

7. Reported Results

Primary outputs (main paper & white paper): - % Improvement (BU vs TD) — mean weekly % difference.

- **t p** — p-value from one-sample t-test.
- **HitRate** — proportion of weeks BU < TD.
- **Binom p** — p-value from binomial test.
- Separate columns for **Units** and **Revenue**.
- Metric: **MAE only**.
- Model: **ARIMA (primary)**; SES and HWES referenced in appendix.

Supporting outputs (appendix): - Additional tables with SMAPE and RMSE metrics.

- Full results for all three models (ARIMA, SES, HWES).

8. Summary Table Structure

Category	Model	U%	Ut	Uh	Up	R%	Rt	Rh	Rp
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Note.

U% = mean % improvement (BU vs TD) based on units. Ut = p-value from one-sample t-test (Units). Uh = Hit Rate (Units). Up = p-value from binomial test (Units). R% = mean % improvement (BU vs TD) based on revenue. Rt = p-value from one-sample t-test (Revenue). Rh = Hit Rate (Revenue). Rp = p-value from binomial test (Revenue). Bold = $p < 0.05$.

9. Planned Output Structure

- **13 Summary Tables:** 7 Location + 6 Product (Units + Revenue combined).
- **1 Headline Table:** aggregate results across all models and categories.

- **Appendix:** full metric/model results (MAE + sMAPE + RMSE × ARIMA, SES, HWES).
 - **Raw data appendix:** all individual forecast results for reproducibility.
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10. Hypotheses

1. **H₁ (Directional Accuracy):** BU forecasts will outperform TD forecasts on a weekly basis significantly more than 50% of the time.
 2. **H₂ (Magnitude of Improvement):** The mean % difference in MAE between BU and TD will be significantly > 0.
 3. **H₃ (Consistency Across Aggregations):** These effects will hold across both product and location hierarchies.
 4. **H₄ (Revenue Robustness):** Directional and magnitude advantages in units will persist when weighted by revenue.
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11. Preregistration Notes

- This preregistration covers analytic intent only; model parameters follow standard automatic selection procedures (R forecast package defaults).
- All tests are two-tailed with $\alpha = 0.05$ unless otherwise specified.
- Any deviations (e.g., alternate data splits or parameter tuning) will be reported in the supplementary materials.